

ISic1204

I.Sicily inscription 1204

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140688

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Περπέγ-
3. νιος
4. ῥεστιτοῦτος
5. ἔζησεν
6. ἔτη λεί.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492808

EDCS 39101568

PHI 140688

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0381 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 199

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